

Data Steward Program of the University of Basel

Development of RDM services and Data Stewardship at the University of Basel

Since 2017, the University of Basel's Research Data Management (RDM) Network has supported researchers across the research data lifecycle, initially through central service and infrastructure providers. In 2021–2022, a President's Board-funded pilot expanded the network to include faculty-embedded data stewards. A train-the-trainer program was introduced to empower them and to strengthen network collaboration. These decentralized data stewards serve as subject-specific first points-of-contact for researchers, offering tailored guidance, connecting researchers to services, and aligning faculty needs with institution-wide RDM solutions.

With support from swissuniversities (B5.2 action line), the data stewardship program was consolidated and extended beyond the pilot phase from January 2023 to June 2025. Key measures included onboarding new data stewards across all faculties, departments and university institutes, implementing a comprehensive training program, developing discipline-specific best practices, and integrating RDM into doctoral training.

Project Results 2023-2025

Between January 2023 and June 2025, the Data Stewardship Program significantly expanded and professionalized RDM support at the University of Basel. Onboarding discussions were held with 18 university units, resulting in the appointment of 19 new data stewards. Currently, [37 data stewards](#) are active across all seven faculties and university institutes.

The train-the-trainer program was continued, providing data stewards with 18 courses over two and a half years, alongside 5 semester kickoff events and 3 exchange meetings for the data stewards.

3 working groups, organized in agile sprints, addressed key university-wide challenges: (1) [handling personal data in research](#), (2) assessing researchers' needs with regard to

collaboration tools for sensitive research data, and (3) [managing data at the end of research projects](#). One sprint resulted in an internal report; the other two led to practical guidelines that have been published on [Zenodo](#).

To support translation of general RDM principles into local workflows, pilot initiatives developed discipline-specific best practices – such as a comprehensive [RDM guide at the Faculty of Psychology](#) and an on-/off-boarding checklist at the Department of Biomedicine – offering adaptable models for other departments.

To raise awareness of the RDM support services and strengthen the visibility of the data stewards, 8 roadshows were conducted across selected faculties and departments.

In collaboration with doctoral programs and graduate schools, 6 pilot courses for doctoral candidates across multiple disciplines were developed and delivered, fostering sustainable collaborations and increasing RDM visibility among early-career researchers.

With regard to the future of RDM at the University of Basel, the revision of the network's governance was important. To ensure the sustainability of the data stewardship program, a permanent position has been created at the University Library to coordinate the RDM Network beyond the project phase.

What's next?

- The [network and the data stewardship program](#) will continue, including training courses and community events for data stewards.
- The coordination of the network is ensured by the Open Science Team of the University Library, and is steered by the Vice President's Office for Research. A strategy group was established to address the future development of the network.
- A follow-up project has been approved by swissuniversities (July 2025 to June 2026), focussing on the interplay of RDM and compliance with the data classification.

We are happy to support or collaborate with you

- Find our data stewards for RDM support: <https://researchdata.unibas.ch/en/services/data-stewards/>
- Come to our training courses and events: <https://researchdata.unibas.ch/en/services/training/>
- Subscribe to our mailing list: <https://researchdata.unibas.ch/en/services/mailling-list/>
- Find information on RDM on our website: <https://researchdata.unibas.ch/en/>
- If you require training courses or input on RDM for researchers or students, or information material, or if you have suggestions or feedback, please let us know: researchdata@unibas.ch

